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Tackling dataset bias with an automated collection of real-world samples

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ABSTRACT The early 21st-century technological advancements tilted the scales towards data-driven learning. Thus, modern machine learning systems rely heavily on data to learn complex models to provide relevant predictions efficiently. Data-driven learning suffers from the nightmare of overfitting, a situation in which the learning process seems to have converged into a model that, unfortunately, lacks generalization power. A way to withstand overfitting is to expand the training dataset with more diverse samples. Typically, this is implemented (particularly in computer vision research, that is of interest in this paper) by multiplying the original sample using several transformations. Although this strategy might seem pretty straightforward, it does not affect any pre-existing dataset bias since the initial distribution remains more or less similar. Ideally, new samples of unseen data have to be found, but the cost of acquiring them one by one is high. This paper presents a novel pipeline combining state-of-the-art modules to create new thematic datasets with low bias automatically. The proposed method was able to acquire and allocate more than 880K previously unseen images to the effect of producing a data collection with that InceptionV3 classified it with 72% accuracy and it achieved 0.0008 performance variance when testing on similar datasets.

INDEX TERMS AI, dataset bias, domain shift, image datasets, machine learning, web search

I. INTRODUCTION

SUPERVISED learning is the method to accurately model a known generator function that produces a data distribution [1]. Very often, engineers and AI practitioners that apply supervised learning need to tackle a phenomenon with a significant impact on the learning process, called overfitting. Overfitting happens when a model captures the underlying pattern and the noise of the data to the extent that it cannot generalize the learned concept and make accurate predictions on unseen data. In cases where model alteration techniques, like simplification, regularization, and ensembling, treat this issue only up to a point the problem lies within the data.

In recent years, another occurrence has been observed that hinders model performance on unseen data. Sometimes, a model performs well on a dataset's held-out samples that simulate an unknown distribution. However, this does not necessarily mean that the model would behave correspondingly well on unseen real-world data. This phenomenon is

termed as 'dataset bias' [2].

Dataset bias occurs when the inclusion of samples within a class follows a specific set of rules. Then, even if a model can learn how to recognize the dataset's classes, it is under the assumption that all distribution instances adhere to the same set of rules. For instance, SUN09 [3] and Caltech101 [4], are generic benchmark datasets that both share a class describing *cars*. Ideally, learning on one and inferring on the other should work fine. However, in practice, this is not the case. According to [5], one dataset portrays the front face of cars, while the other depicts them mostly from the aside.

Depending on the application, bias is not harmful by itself. Consider, for example, the case of quality control on a production line, where one needs to ensure that a defect is never missed due to safety implications. Thus, introducing bias towards recognizing defective samples costs less than missing ones. However, a benchmark should ideally be a representative instance of the natural world, so the computer

vision community would focus on trying to deal with the problem instead of modeling the dataset. This observation has been pointed out by Hand [6]: "*However, this also means that there will be some overfitting both to the individual data sets in the collection and the collection as a whole. That is, some methods will do well on data sets in the collection purely by chance. Indeed, the more successful the collection is in the sense that more and more people use it for comparative assessments, the more serious this problem will become.*" Acquiring such datasets with real-world distributions is an impossible endeavor, practically infeasible. Perhaps, the best course of action would be to sample different and as many distribution instances as possible to approximate the description of the real world.

Handpicking such samples is cost ineffective, time-consuming, and prone to mistakes. Automatic data acquisition from resources such as the Web is not a trivial assignment since the lack of a sophisticated methodology is expected to lead to a noisy, imbalanced, and even error-prone assortment of data. A wide range of challenges is likely to be encountered when designing frameworks to undertake this task, like (a) irrelevant content removal, (b) correct data to class assignment, (c) composition of suitable queries, and (d) rectification of corrupted data. In addition, common concerns exist in dataset formalization procedures, including (a) balancing of samples per class, (b) dealing with conflicting content, (c) constructing and leveraging inclusion or mutual exclusion strategies, and (d) handling missing data. These are all issues to be considered during the creation of benchmark datasets [7], [8], landmark recognition [9], as well as in more generic ones [10]. Therefore, assembling a formal AI-useful dataset from the Web, even to expand existing datasets, is still challenging.

Motivated by the challenges above, this paper proposes a pipeline that acquires samples from the Web to remedy the dataset bias problem. Emphasis is given to producing a robust and accurate candidate selection method based on removing irrelevant content and preserving a ranking of the most representative samples. The main contribution of this work is a pipeline with novel combinations of modules which

- 1) can effortlessly create a dataset given a list of labels,
- 2) can expand/augment existing datasets with previously unseen real-world samples,
- 3) requires minimal to none human involvement, and
- 4) mitigate dataset bias.

The following sections include a review of the relevant literature, a presentation of the novel pipeline, and experimental verification of the proposed procedure.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

A. DATASET BIAS

The mismatch between datasets used in the pattern recognition domain for developing better algorithms in laboratory conditions and real applications has been discussed as early as in [6]. It has been illustrated through examples that in

many, perhaps most, real classification problems, the data points in the design set are not, in fact, randomly drawn from the same distribution as the data points to which the classifier will be applied, e.g., the real world.

In the computer vision domain, this observation became widely known with the work of Torralba and Efros [2], in which it was pointed out that the cross-evaluation of categories shared between different datasets led to a lower performance than expected. The authors attribute this phenomenon to the data collection procedure, which can be biased by human and systematic factors, resulting in distribution mismatch between datasets.

A series of works focused on overcoming this problem, mainly by developing classifiers with better generalization properties [5]. Datasets with common categories, such as SUN [3], LabelMe [12], PascalVOC [13], Caltech101 [4], and Imagenet [14], have been used to cross-evaluate the performance of such classifiers on the shared classes. The problem of partially overlapping label sets among different datasets has also been considered [15].

The computer vision community became increasingly aware that existing benchmarks presented a characteristic signature that differed from one dataset to the other. This observation spawned the related domain shift problem, e.g., performance discrepancies appear on source and target image datasets with different marginal probability distributions when training on one and inferring on the other. Shared representations to eliminate the original distribution mismatch, such as subspace data embedding [16], [17], metric [18], [19] and vocabulary learning [20] have been presented. Other works demonstrated that deep learning architectures might produce domain invariant descriptors through a highly nonlinear transformation of the original features [21], [22].

Domain adaptation techniques have been well-studied [23]–[25]. These approaches intrinsically rely on having more than one dataset to observe the shift in the domain; otherwise, the dataset bias problem is concealed in the first place. To this extent, the authors of the present work share the same perspective with [2] that is, "all the datasets are trying to represent the same domain – our visual world", therefore here, it is proposed to construct a visually robust dataset with limited bias from scratch.

B. DATASET CONSTRUCTION

In the early years of image dataset formation, manual acquisition and data annotation were preferable approaches. In situ data acquisition was not an uncommon practice [27], [28]. It involved an expensive overhead prior to analyzing the data and constructing the actual dataset, i.e., setting up a camera, removing obstacles from the scene, avoiding capturing humans and human parts to preserve their anonymity, and finally composing the frame [29]–[31]. Exploiting the Web as a source for manually gathering images is a labor-intensive assignment. This task consists of (a) querying the Web given a few keywords, (b) downloading the content, and (c) exhaustively manually annotating the downloaded samples to

clear out unwanted material. When human annotators collaborate on a task, annotation normalization and alignment must be applied. Benchmark datasets, like the ImageNet [14] (a dataset which took years to get completed), CIFAR-10 [10], ETH-Food-101 [33], are striking examples of datasets constructed by relying extensively on human expertise.

Several frameworks have been proposed to reduce the overhead of manual formulation. In [32], visual information has been used to re-rank retrieved images from the Web. However, this method relies on the statistical modeling of bootstrapped classifiers to discard unrelated images. [35] used active learning methods to iteratively improve the confidence of unlabelled samples using existing labeled data. Early attempts to automatically construct image datasets involved retrieving images and textual information via Web search. In [34], latent topics are extracted from the textual information, and voting classifiers assign them to the related images. In [36], a sequential framework was proposed, which takes advantage of the ranking information for the first few results offered by a Web search engine. Under the assumption that those images fall correctly into the requested label, a binary classifier was incrementally refined to assess whether those images are relevant or not. Finding content in such an uncontrolled environment might be faster than other approaches, but introduces additional challenges, viz., the sample per class distribution might not be the desired, and object co-occurrence is often disregarded. As discussed in [37], this problem is ubiquitous in the food image recognition domain, where various image descriptors have been used to extract local and global features to recognize multiple-food photos considering co-occurrence statistics. In [38], the same authors employed a manifold learning approach to improve results in that domain.

More recent approaches focus on enriching a dataset with subcategories by performing multiple query requests instead of just a single one [39]. To achieve this, vocabulary-based resources are utilized, like the WordNet [41], ConceptNet [42] and the Google Books Ngram Corpus [43]. Using synonyms or word pairs to multiply the facets of a keyword can substantially increase the number of candidate samples [44]. However, unwanted content due to word ambiguity will certainly appear [45], and a mechanism for discarding it has to be developed. Since word-pairs can be of arbitrary length, word-to-word distance has been applied in reducing the candidate queries [46]. Nevertheless, the query composition complexity challenge for unambiguous Web retrieval is only partly addressed.

The Web is regarded as a valuable resource, especially when aiming to use it for acquiring extensive collections of data for practical AI applications. However, collecting data blindly with no treatment can quickly become futile. To meet the challenges in this task, we propose a pipeline attuned to creating AI-usable datasets with data acquired from the Web. This pipeline consists of several modules, which collaborate to construct a dataset. Such a process begins with the definition of the aim, the requirements, and

the expectations of the dataset. The source from which the labels of the classes are taken has to be credible. For instance, ontologies could be employed to construct a formal list of labels around a specific topic. The Europeana ontology [47], [48] for cultural artifacts, or the Amalthea hierarchy [49] for food dishes, or the International Code of Zoological Nomenclature (ICZN) [50] for animal taxonomies are a few examples of said ontologies. As an additional advantage, ontologies usually provide rich information about the relations among the objects they describe. This way, keyword or query expansion is possible without introducing text mining and understanding complexities. More than one popular search engine can be used to retrieve image data from the Web; engines that provide indexed content according to a query [32]. Still, it is expected that undesired content in the form of duplicate and irrelevant images will appear in the retrieved results.

III. MODELLING THE EFFECT OF DUPLICATE AND IRRELEVANT SAMPLES WITHIN THE TRAINING SET

This section presents an *in vitro* ablation study to demonstrate the need for duplicate and irrelevant samples' removal when creating image datasets for pattern recognition tasks. Two benchmark datasets and a robust classifier display the effects of including that kind of noise at different ratios.

The Food-101 (ETHZ [33]) dataset is considered for this study as the target domain for the classifier to learn. It contains 1000 sample images for each of its 101 classes of food dishes. The dataset is split into training and testing sets with 75-25% ratios, respectively, according to the initial publication instructions. The ImageNet [14] is used as a generator of irrelevant samples. A random portion is retrieved regardless of label and class, according to the needs of each noise addition stage.

InceptionV3 [40] with its weights initialized on ImageNet was chosen as a benchmark classifier. This architecture was chosen mainly due to its past state-of-the-art performance, ease of training and parameter configuration, and, last but not least, its wide adoption and usage in the available relevant literature. The top layer has been substituted to reflect the 101-class problem at hand, same as in [51].

The procedure begins by using the benchmark (Food-101) for training, so a baseline classification performance is calculated. Then, the training set is altered to represent an instance in which noise, in the form of duplicate and/or irrelevant samples, is inserted. In this process, 'noise' samples replace valid ones progressively for each type of noise. The model is re-initialized and trained for each dataset instance. Throughout these experiments, the test set remains the same, with no addition of noise.

As per standard practice, the model is also trained with affine transformations of the training samples to reduce overfitting phenomena. The whole procedure (with and without augmentation via transformations) is repeated ten times, and the mean TOP-1 accuracy and standard deviation are reported in TABLE 1.

TABLE 1: Degradation of a classifier’s performance when adding duplicate and irrelevant samples: (a) without augmentation; (b) with augmentation

(a)	Duplicate (%)	Irrelevant (%)		
		10	25	50
10		0.736(±0.006)	0.734(±0.004)	0.711(±0.008)
25		0.725(±0.004)	0.728(±0.005)	0.698(±0.003)
50		0.692(±0.009)	0.7(±0.007)	0.691(±0.009)
baseline		0.747(±0.007)		

(b)	Duplicate (%)	Irrelevant (%)		
		10	25	50
10		0.793(±0.012)	0.789(±0.014)	0.751(±0.012)
25		0.778(±0.005)	0.761(±0.009)	0.746(±0.010)
50		0.746(±0.006)	0.765(±0.013)	0.732(±0.007)
baseline		0.803(±0.008)		

FIGURE 1: Model performance with the inclusion of noise at various proportions

FIGURE 1a & 1b depict the mean values of TABLE 1. As anticipated, noise in the combined form of duplicate and irrelevant samples negatively affects a model’s generalization performance. The latter is due to duplicate samples offering no information to the learner other than what has not already seen. On the other hand, irrelevant samples might boost the generalization capacity of a model since it struggles to make up features fitting samples that should not be there in the first place. Notice that, in small percentages, both kinds of noises do not dramatically affect the performance of the model in comparison with them being absent. However, the more the noise, the more the performance degradation, even in cases where their proportion is not the same. Thus, caution should be exercised when efforts to acquire samples from different distributions for a given domain situate in uncontrolled yet rich environments, such as the Web.

IV. PROPOSED PIPELINE

This paper proposes a pipeline to construct datasets of images by gathering samples from the Web and assigning them to classes with respect to a list of predefined keywords (i.e., the class labels). A high-level graphical overview is presented in FIGURE 2. A list of keywords is used to query the Web for data. The list of query keywords can either be anything that a practitioner provides manually or terms automatically retrieved from an ontology, provided that a parsing mechanism is used. Then the images collected from the Web are processed via modules to filter out irrelevant and duplicate content. Irrelevant images are considered those outside the

FIGURE 2: The proposed pipeline

scope of the categories described by the query keywords. Duplicate images are the exact or geometrically transformed copies of other images in the dataset. These definitions and the related policy are followed throughout the data collection procedure. No duplicate images are allowed within a given class and across the dataset.

A. IRRELEVANT DETECTION

A majority voting decision of binary classifiers was used to reject irrelevant content from the stream of the retrieved samples. The majority voting is similar to unweighted averaging. Nevertheless, instead of averaging the output probability, it counts the votes of all the predicted labels from the base learners. It makes a final prediction using the label with

the most votes. Equivalently, it takes an unweighted average using the label from base learners and chooses the label with the most significant value. This notion decides whether an image is relevant to the desired dataset or should be discarded.

Three state-of-the-art deep architectures (InceptionV3 [40], MobileNet [58], and ResNet-50 [57]) are being used in this work to perform binary classification. All they require is a binary class dataset, which represents the scope of what is considered relevant and what is not. Hence, when a sample reaches this module, the three deep neural network binary classifiers independently vote on whether it is relevant. Subsequently, the majority outcome of said votes is the final decision: to discard it or to let it move to the next filtering module (deduplication).

B. DUPLICATE DETECTION

A deduplication mechanism was developed to reject duplicate images, leveraging previous work in duplicate image detection, which has been applied broadly in many applications, such as forensics and closed-loop systems. Several methods have been proposed for duplicate image detection, including, but not limited to, relying on textbook image descriptors [52], [53], as well as bespoke deep neural networks [55], [56], [60]. Typically, a feature extractor combined with a distance measure compares any two images to determine their similarity. The application of a threshold defines the degree of similarity, which in our case, reduces to being a duplicate or not. A reliable method is needed to (a) bring closer those images that are either the same or geometrically transformed copies of one another while at the same time, (b) separate those that have just a visual resemblance or are entirely different.

Moreover, as this pipeline aims to construct a large-scale dataset, the deduplication method must scale well as more and more data are being collected into the candidate pool. Hence, the way these descriptors are stored affects their retrieval speed. If these descriptors were put as items into a simple list, then the search algorithm would be required to query all items one by one, resulting in a square search space. Although the triangle inequality holds, the search space reduces from n^2 to $\frac{n^2-n}{2}$, where n is the number of items. Yet, the computational complexity still reaches an impractical $O(n^2)$.

To tackle the search mechanism's computational complexity, a Burkhar-Keller Tree (BK-Tree) structure [66] has been exploited. It is a tree-based data structure used to find the near-matches to a string query. The original implementation performed approximate matching in strings and was used for spell checking [59]. The critical property that constitutes a BK-Tree advantageous as a searching instrument is that it exhibits low complexity. To achieve that, it exploits two functions, namely: triangle inequality and Levenshtein distance. The triangle inequality bounds the solution within upper and lower limits and allows for the item's ordering. The Levenshtein distance counts the operations needed to transform a

FIGURE 3: A Query image (middle) is compared with two Test images, where only one is a duplicate (bottom). Equation (1) applies.

query word to a match, e.g., the next node to visit, while traversing the structure. Finally, the tree structure minimizes the search space, reducing its complexity to $O(\log n)$.

In this work, we propose two slight modifications to the BK-tree, namely (a) to store and query the binary feature vectors extracted by the Locality-sensitive hashing (LSH) algorithms and (b) to use Hamming instead of Levenshtein distance. Hamming distance $\left(\sum_{u_i \neq v_i}^i 1\right)$ is a classic metric, as it is a mapping to the set of real numbers (\mathbb{R}) with zero (0) minimum that corresponds to the distance to oneself, it is commutative and satisfies the condition that only equal entities have a zero distance and the triangle inequality holds:

$$\begin{aligned}
 d(u, v) &\geq 0 \\
 d(u, v) &= 0 \iff u = v \\
 d(u, v) &= d(v, u) \\
 d(u, v) &\leq d(u, w) + d(w, v)
 \end{aligned} \tag{1}$$

It can substitute the original metric in LSH algorithms to perform the same task and be applied to the setting of binary vectors instead. All properties of the original search mechanism are guaranteed to continue to exist. This is shown in FIGURE 3 where the features vectors are extracted from three different images of the same subject (label); in particular, the query image in the middle is different with test⁽¹⁾, whereas test⁽²⁾ is a manipulated version of the query image (contrast and tone enhancement, slight rotation and cropping).

Finally, the deduplication module in the proposed pipeline employs three LSH methods [65] that are fast feature extractors and reliable at detecting most affine transformations, namely (a) the average image hash, (b) the perceptual hash, and (c) the difference hash. They produce binary and compact

feature vectors, making them computationally important. Hamming distance fits nicely as a metric for these descriptors because it measures the number of transforming steps a vector needs to take to become another. In other words, the steps required for a query to transform into a test vector. An exclusive BK-tree is constructed for each descriptor. Each time an image is encountered, its signature is extracted and compared with all candidate image hashes within the tree structures. A majority voting approach decides whether an image is duplicate or not; no tiebreaker is needed since there are three voters with equal voting weight. The query hash is stored at its respective BK-tree, if and only if there was no duplicate decision outcome. Additionally, the query image is added to the candidate pool.

V. EXPERIMENTS AND DISCUSSION

This section details the assessment of the performance of the proposed approach in creating an AI-useful image dataset using Web samples. It also details whether sampling from many sources mitigates the dataset bias phenomenon. The domain of food recognition is chosen for the experimental procedure. There are already too many food datasets publicly available [63] for the computer vision community to experiment with and develop approaches for tasks such as dish and ingredient recognition and calorie calculation based on volume. Among these datasets, two versions of Food-101 are available, the originally published (ETHZ [33]) and its twin (UPMC [54]), which, although share the same categories, they have been collected from different sources. Hence, the choice of using these datasets as a case study presents noticeable practical advantages, such as the capacity for (a) the validation of the pipeline's ability to construct formal datasets, (b) the direct observation of any dataset bias between the published benchmarks, and (c) the cross-evaluation of whether sampling from many different sources fixes the dataset bias.

A. IRRELEVANT SAMPLE REMOVER

A binary class dataset has been constructed to train the three classifiers (InceptionV3, MobileNet, and ResNet-50). Samples were taken from benchmark datasets to populate the relevant/not Relevant (food/non Food) classes. Specifically, for the food images, random samples were taken from FoodX-251 [61], and ISIA Food-200 [62], so 100K images were collected. On the other hand, the non Food samples were taken from benchmark datasets with generic categories, such as PascalVOC, Caltech-101, and ImageNet. Similarly, 100K images were taken from them. Special attention was given in the latter case, so the categories and their samples depicted no food.

The training procedure followed the idea of using classifiers pre-trained on ImageNet to extract features. A set of classification layers consisting of a Global Average Pooling, a Dense Layer of 512 neurons, 20% Dropout, and the final 2-neurons Dense classifier was attached at the top of the model. The model is used to predict whether a sample is relevant or not. As an optimizer, the SGD was chosen to

TABLE 2: Irrelevant detection performances

InceptionV3	MobileNet	ResNet-50	Accuracy
Yes	No	No	0.9937
No	Yes	No	0.9966
No	No	Yes	0.9963
Yes	No	Yes	0.9941
No	Yes	Yes	0.9965
Yes	Yes	Yes	0.9968

minimize the binary cross-entropy loss function. Empirically, it was found that after ten epochs, no significant performance improvement was gained. Based on the losses, no overfitting was detected, as shown in FIGURE 4.

This approach exploits robust classifiers, which, based on the validation outcome on the test set, should agree on most of their individual decisions, anyway. However, in case of disagreement, the voting mechanism provides the tiebreaker with the final decision. Based on the proposed approach regarding the irrelevant detection mechanism, discarding unwanted samples is both fast and accurate, as shown in TABLE 2.

B. DUPLICATE SAMPLE REMOVER

An experiment was conducted, similar to the one proposed in [64], to find the optimal threshold for the image hashing algorithms. A random subset was taken, which comprised 2000 unique images from the CIFAR-10 dataset. For each image, the following transformations were applied, producing 40 images: (a) contrast adjustment; (b) despeckling; (c) flipping; (d) the values of the R, G, and B channels were increased by 10% respectively; (e) cropping by 5%, 10%, 20%, and 30%, preserving the center region of the original image and then resizing to the original size; (f) downsampling the image by 10%, 20%, 30%, 40%, 50%, 70% and 90%; (g) format conversion from JPEG to GIF; (h) an outer frame of random color was added four times to the image, where the size of the frame is 10% of the image, respectively; (i) rotating by 90°, 180° and 270°; (j) scaling up by 2, 4, and 8 times, scaling down by 2, 4, and 8 times; (k) intensity adjustment by 70%, 80%, 90%, 110% and 120%; and (l) saturation adjustment by 70%, 80%, 90%, 110% and 120%. The transformations resulted in a total of 82000 images, of which the signatures were extracted respectively with each image hashing method. Distances and confusion matrices were calculated for all images. The desired threshold θ is the one that minimizes the following function:

$$\arg \min_{\theta} |FN - FP| \quad (2)$$

The point at which the false negative (FN) line intersects with the false positive (FP) one is the threshold θ , as FIGURE 5 illustrates. Another sample of 20000 images is taken from the same dataset mutually exclusive to the training set to test the thresholds. Then, 500 are randomly selected and undergo the

FIGURE 4: Binary cross-entropy for InceptionV3 (left), MobileNet (middle) and ResNet50 (right) while training on the custom food/nonFood dataset

TABLE 3: Duplicate detection performance

Avg	Diff	Perc	Recall	Precision	F1
Yes	No	No	0.807	0.93	0.861
No	Yes	No	0.801	0.973	0.879
No	No	Yes	0.821	0.982	0.894
Yes	Yes	No	0.811	0.982	0.888
Yes	No	Yes	0.828	0.899	0.862
No	Yes	Yes	0.838	0.958	0.894
Yes	Yes	Yes	0.843	0.961	0.898

transformations mentioned above. This results in a test set of 40000 images. The achieved cross-validated F1 score for $\theta^{(\alpha)} = 3$ (average image hash), $\theta^{(d)} = 14$ (difference hash) and $\theta^{(p)} = 14$ was 89.8%, as reported in TABLE 3.

C. CONSTRUCTING FOOD-101 FROM THE WEB

A query list was gathered from the 101 labels composing the Food-101 classes. These queries were given to custom-tailored crawlers to seek content at four search engines and two image repositories—the sample collection comprised 606 crawling tasks performed in parallel. A total of 885,662 images were collected. As expected, for popular foods, the samples were far more than those of less known dishes, as shown in FIGURE 6, which displays the distribution of samples per class. For comparison to the benchmark dataset, the green dashed line at the one thousand mark signifies the FOOD-101 (ETHZ) counts of samples per class.

Estimating whether an image is relevant to the scope of the dataset needs no memory of previous samples or knowledge of the image’s label. This procedure begins when collection tasks report that they have completed their job. In this manner, the samples were filtered regarding their relevance to the dataset. 111.6K (12.6%) were discarded as irrelevant, and the rest were kept as valid.

In contrast with the less demanding relevance filtering, the deduplication mechanism needs to know the label a sample will be assigned to and all unique samples processed before it. A BK-tree structure per class label and descriptor was the unique sample storage. Thus, this module extracted its LSH feature vectors for any incoming sample and searched the respective tree for a match. In case none was found, the

sample was characterized as unique and stored within the structure; otherwise, it was discarded as a duplicate. Hence, 129.3K (14.6%) images were further rejected.

Finally, after cleaning out the unwanted content, the dataset resulted in 644,800 images (5190.37(\pm 1459.88) samples per class). That is, an increase **538.3%** over the ETHZ Food-101 dataset (which contains 101K images in total) or **6.3** more samples were collected for every benchmark image. FIGURE 7 (right) shows the ratio between the valid, the irrelevant, and the duplicate samples¹. For practical purposes, the discarded samples being irrelevant or duplicates were kept for further experimentation.

Implementation-wise, the modules above were developed as individual software services (SaaS). Containerization and job orchestration were essential design details that contributed to the speed and parallelism of tasks. If multi-processing and multi-threaded practices were neglected, it would have resulted in collecting the samples in more than 1100 hrs (roughly 45 days), removing irrelevant samples in 370 hrs (15 days), and rejecting duplicate content in 580 hrs (24 days). Such an approach would require a total of 84 days of operational time. In contrast, the achieved data collection time was **88.25 hrs**, decreasing more than an order of magnitude. In addition, the achieved irrelevant and duplicate sample rejection lasted **8.5 hrs** and **22.75 hrs** respectively, a decrease of more than an order of magnitude in both cases, for the exact same infrastructure (computing and networking)². The total amount of time needed from start to finish in order to construct the dataset used in the following experiments was **103.43 hrs** or slightly more than 4 days, which is a 95.23% decrease in time with respect to a typical serial design (no sophisticated parallel processing whatsoever).

D. ABLATION STUDY

An additional ablation study was performed to establish the need for the proposed rejection (filtering) modules. To be able

¹The color coding corresponds with FIGURE 2.

²The time reported in the case of irrelevant and duplicate samples rejection is the cumulative operational time since the modules ran asynchronously

FIGURE 5: Finding the distance that minimizes the parameter θ

FIGURE 6: The distribution of samples per class. The green dashed line signifies the samples per class of FOOD-101 (ETHZ).

to compare with the earlier ablation study, which examined the need for filtering out duplicate and irrelevant content, the same deep learning architecture was used before, namely the InceptionV3.

The samples acquired from the Web are considered an assortment of data and cannot be applied in typical classification experiments with fairness. To construct fair training/testing sets, a two-step mutual exclusion rule was applied as follows:

- 1) a test set was sampled without including duplicates
- 2) all samples within the test set were examined for duplicates on the rest of the data. Any existing duplicates that were found during this procedure were removed

Hence, no shared examples exist within the training and test

sets for the rest of the experiments.

The four cases this ablation study considers are with regard to the training set, as follows:

- using all the unfiltered data
- using irrelevant-filtered data
- using duplicate-filtered data
- using irrelevant- and duplicate-filtered data

TABLE 4 presents the performance of InceptionV3 for all dataset instances. The results coincided with the declining trend observed and presented earlier in the *in vitro* study. Having no irrelevant but many duplicate samples granted no performance gains, besides increasing the demand for training resources, such as memory and time. On the other hand, having irrelevant data decreased the model’s performance, as

FIGURE 7: The relative contribution of search engines (left). The ratio between the rejected samples and those that were considered valid (right)

TABLE 4: Evaluating InceptionV3 performance with and without the use of the rejection modules. "Yes" indicates the use of the module; "No" otherwise.

Duplicates	Irrelevant	Accuracy
No	No	0.682
No	Yes	0.691
Yes	No	0.707
Yes	Yes	0.725

expected, since no relevant to the learning problem useful information could be extracted from them. The worst and best cases are the two opposites regarding using no filtering at all and rejecting noise data altogether, respectively.

E. WIDER SAMPLING FIXES DATASET BIAS

Using the labels of the Food-101 dataset to construct another one sampled from a multitude of Web resources presented the practical advantages of (a) having two benchmark dataset versions of the same classes, allowed to study the dataset bias phenomenon first hand and subsequently (b) the effect the more exhaustive sampling has on the bias phenomenon.

This section describes a cross-evaluation experiment that was carried out to assess the discrepancy. For consistency purposes, InceptionV3 was used once more as a classifier. The top layer has been substituted similarly to the earlier experiments to be fit for the 101-class problem. The architecture was trained for 25 epochs, at which point performance improvements plateaued. Also, this experiment explicitly used no transfer learning techniques at all. Hence the deep learning architecture has been trained for all its layers from the start. The data split for training and testing was according to the initial publication instructions for both datasets.

Training on ETHZ and testing on itself performed significantly higher than when testing on UPMC. This was not the case when the opposite scenario was addressed. The classifier trained on UPMC and tested on ETHZ performed compara-

bly well as if it was tested with itself, albeit less accurately. The mismatch in the first case probably happened due to the selection of samples being biased on ETHZ's behalf. Perhaps the architecture was able to learn representations that easily model sample inclusion rules.

On the other hand, the makers of UPMC's version claimed that they queried a single search engine; thus, the included images contain samples of different origins and wrongly assigned labels, resulting in a comparable yet noisy dataset. In the latter case having looser rules regarding a sample's inclusion resulted in a classifier that learned more general representations. However, the drop in performance regarding the UPMC/ETHZ test is an issue that hints that neither versions capture well the real-world domain shaped by its classes.

Moving forward, the dataset that was constructed by the proposed approach is introduced to the experimental setup. A 75-25% stratified split was performed on the dataset³. The same classifier (as in architecture, hyperparameters, and training procedure) is trained on the newly constructed version and tested on all other versions consecutively. Additionally, the previous models were tested on this version too. Cross-evaluation TOP-1 and TOP-5 accuracy performances are reported on TABLE 5 and TABLE 6 respectively.

The ETHZ version seems to be the one that suffers most from dataset bias since testing on all other versions could not match that performance. In particular, testing on the new version produced an outcome that cannot be considered beneficial: a classification score of less than 50%. As mentioned earlier, training on UPMC and testing on ETHZ resulted in comparable results with testing on itself. However, testing on the version produced by the proposed approach resulted in just above 50% accuracy (top-1). The constructed

³Common samples with ETHZ and UPMC were removed too; 657 and 4271, respectively. In proportion, this is 0.65% and 4.7% of these datasets

Trained		Tested			
		ETHZ	UPMC	OURS	\pm
ETHZ	0.80324	0.52082	0.45622	0.184	
UPMC	0.6083	0.6958	0.5199	0.087	
OURS	0.70372	0.66851	0.72548	0.028	

TABLE 5: Cross-evaluation of Top-1 accuracy on Food-101 and its variations

Trained		Tested			
		ETHZ	UPMC	OURS	\pm
ETHZ	0.9367	0.7077	0.658	0.148	
UPMC	0.7855	0.8427	0.7039	0.069	
OURS	0.8684	0.8125	0.8986	0.043	

TABLE 6: Cross-evaluation of Top-5 accuracy on Food-101 and its variations

FIGURE 8: (left) Top-1 accuracy cross-evaluation on Food-101 and its variations; (right) Top-5 accuracy cross-evaluation on Food-101 and its variations

dataset seems to be a useless assortment of data at this point. Yet, a top-1 72.5% as an accuracy performance when training on the new version and testing on itself suggests otherwise. Moreover, testing the latter on the twin benchmark versions produces meaningful and equivalent to itself results. Notice how small the variance between performances is in FIGURE 8 (left). The standard deviation in TABLE 5 and TABLE 6 reveal this observation. Similar issues can be noticed when examining the top-5 performances e.g., TABLE 6, FIGURE 8 (right). The ETHZ version is secluded to itself. Meaningful results appear when using the UPMC version, yet the variance of performances is big amongst versions. Stable performances appear when using the newly constructed dataset.

VI. CONCLUSIONS

In this work, an important phenomenon is studied that many benchmark datasets suffer from, the dataset bias, a phenomenon by which a collection of data is not descriptive of the whole domain it represents—learning to transfer knowledge from one domain to a different one deals with a similar but not the same problem. In any case, a dataset is intended to reflect a real-world domain unless it was designed explicitly not to. Another major challenge is to create large datasets in automated ways and guarantee their usability.

To this end, paper proposes a method to automatically construct non-biased datasets by sampling many different sources to handle these issues. The proposed approach uses a list of keywords to query Web-based resources, then it collects samples and discards all those that are duplicates or irrelevant to the scope of the dataset. The paper provides evidence that such noise data degrade the performance of

classification tasks.

The advantages coming with the proposed method for constructing a dataset are (a) it can build a dataset fast, (b) it scales nicely to many more classes, and (c) it allows for looser sample inclusion criteria to occur by imposing a hard rule on excluding duplicate and irrelevant content.

Therefore, the proposed method can be used, for instance, if a classifier has reached its potential given a dataset, and no model alteration techniques or virtual augmentations increase its performance. Broader sampling can be used to learn more general representations or a portion of it to be used to augment the dataset with unseen data.

The weaknesses of the proposed method are mainly two (a) it needs a robust classifier for deciding whether a sample is relevant to the scope of the dataset, and, as a consequence, (b) in non-thematically uniform datasets, constructing the non-relevant class to train the relevant/irrelevant classifier can be cumbersome. Thus, the proposed method scales well for thematic datasets, such as food-related ones (that we tested). A different approach is needed in other cases where a dataset might contain classes of broad interest.

ETHZ and UPMC Food-101 (the twin benchmark datasets) were used for the empirical study. They presented a practical advantage, namely, they share the same class labels, although their data come from different sampling protocols. Thus, they were used as a cross-evaluation test-bed. Throughout the experiments, InceptionV3 was used as a classifier, mainly for consistency reasons. In most cases, it was trained from scratch following the same training procedure.

Three deep learning models are compared with each other. All were trained on Food-101, but one for each version, the ETHZ, the UPMC, and OURS, respectively. The model

trained on ETHZ performs remarkably, but only to itself. The model trained on UPMC learned more general representations than the previous model, yet its performance is subpar on the other two datasets. In contrast, based on the procedure proposed in this work, the model trained on the newly constructed dataset performed comparably well on all three datasets.

In conclusion, this work presented a pipeline consisting of a combination of filtering modules that, in an automated way, can construct a dataset of images with real-world samples acquired from the Web. The experiments presented in this work show that more exhaustive sampling, as in sampling from many different sources, alleviates dataset bias. We are upgrading this method with sample selectivity and query expansion techniques to balance the number of samples per class without sacrificing the generalization properties of broader sampling.

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